

Title	Minutes on the feedback meeting 1 with user panels for the Footprint and Time-series Analysis service
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Table of Content

1. Minutes of the 1st footprint service user panel consultation	3
1.1 Comments on the aerosols/reactive gases footprint service	4
1.2 Comments on the vertical profile footprint service	4
1.3 Comments on the GHG footprint services	5
2. Minutes of the 1st Time series Analysis service user panel consultation	6
2.1 Information Tab and frame of the application	6
2.2 Search Datasets Tab	6
2.3 Select Datasets	7
2.4 Filter data	8
2.5 Data analysis	8
2.5.1 Exploratory analysis	8
2.5.2 Trend analysis	9
2.5.3 Multivariate analysis	9
2.6 General feedback and perspectives	9
2.7 General feedback from the panel:	9
2.8 Presentation of the VA services feedback form by Lise	10

1. Minutes of the 1st footprint service user panel consultation

Participants:

- ICOS ERIC-CP/Lund University (GHG footprints)
 - Alex Vermeulen – chair
 - Ute Karstens
 - Zois Zogopoulos
 - Angeliki Adamaki
 - Claudio D’Onofrio
- NILU (aerosols/reactive gases)
 - Richard Rud
 - Nikolaos Evangeliou
 - Sabine Eckhardt
- CNRS (vertical profiles)
 - Pawel Wolff
 - Damien Boulanger

The ATMO ACCESS footprint service feedback meeting with the user panel for this service was held on 29 September 2023 through a zoom meeting from 10:30 until 12:00 CEST.

The meeting was attended by 4 users from the invited panel of 6 persons. 2 members cancelled because of time constraints. One of the users had interest in both the aerosols/reactive footprint gases and vertical profile services and two users have concentrated on the GHG footprint service. However, all participants, also from the project partners participated and engaged in the discussions and commented on each other’s services.

All 3 footprint services (aerosols/reactive gases, greenhouse gases and vertical profiles) presented the status of the service followed by a detailed discussion on the experiences of the users.

The footprint services are available from a central switchboard at the ATMO ACCESS website at <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/#/>. Access requires login through the Aeris SSO system. This to enable and ensure that personal information gathered during the use of the services is kept safe and correct. However, the Aeris SSO proved to cause difficulties for users to register, as registration requires that accounts are verified by replying to an email sent to the registered email address of the user. These emails sometimes arrive with a big delay of up to several days or not at all. When that delay is too large, validation will fail because of a timeout in the system and when emails do not arrive at all, user access of course is also not granted. This needs to be fixed with high priority to not limit the uptake of the VA services. When users managed to get through they appreciated the possibility to use the ORCID login.

1.1 Comments on the aerosols/reactive gases footprint service

Link available at: <https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/>

- Impressive amount of footprints and data available through a simple and intuitive tool when you know what the data is about
- No mention of ATMO ACCESS on the flexpart product pages (like <https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/data-access>), there the logo is replaced with FLEXPART text instead of ATMO ACCESS. Only reference to ATMO ACCESS is in footer of page with copyright (is there copyright to ATMO-ACCESS?)
- Question is whether the resources for computing needed thus far (millions of cpuh) for the footprints is sustainable (use Sigma2 Norwegian facility)
- The feature of providing the age spectra on regional contributions was very much appreciated and considered very useful
- The VIEW DATA option should display the data as text from the onset instead of a link to the file
- Not all the options in the interface have descriptive labels
- The product view only shows the station ids to select the datasets, would be good to also show station names and display a small map next to the data product to show the station location and change from station to station for the product
- Would appreciate to download a batch of footprint data for multiple stations, months, now user has to click through each combination of station and month
- Improved documentation would be useful
- Where available, observations matching the modelled concentrations in time and place would be nice
- A simple training video on how to use the service would be appreciated
- For (massive) machine to machine download a simple API would be useful
- Other gases are promised on the service title but not there yet

1.2 Comments on the vertical profile footprint service

Link available at: <https://services.iagos-data.fr/atmo-access/footprint>

- Very nice and attractive looking tool, really interactive, lots of options
- Good to have observations integrated with model results
- Download of footprints is not available nor planned. Download of profiles data (IAGOS observations and CO contribution calculated by the SOFT-IO tool) will be implemented soon.
- Time period search criteria will be added. Leading to a refined list of airports (only those visited during the period).

- Suggestion to have emissions per country traceable, now only regional. But after discussion it has been agreed it would be too controversial.
- Labels in plots (e.g. regions, L2, GFAS) should be better explained
- Would be nice to add the plotting of other IAGOS variables with the CO profile (e.g. O3 profile).
- Please add differentiation between natural and anthropogenic contributions
- Plan to provide data in NRT. Depends on availability of emission inventories.

1.3 Comments on the GHG footprint services

Links available at: <https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/worker/#> and <https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/viewer/#>

- Easy to get lost between the different windows as back button is only at the bottom of the page which might require lots of scrolling in case of a long list of queued, running or finished jobs
- Users' email addresses should not be publicly visible in the job queue (GDPR)
- Typo in the selection of source contributions (Biosperic->Biospheric)
- No uncertainty information in the footprint results and calculated concentrations
- Map should discern mountain and surface sites
- Should provide guidance on selecting the correct sampling height for mountain stations depending on model resolution for topography
- Methane information lacking, now just carbon dioxide but methane will be added soon
- Map shows too many stations, consider showing a subset with multiple-year and observations timeseries available at first, with switch to also show stations with short timeseries available.

Note:

Next user feedback meeting should reverse the order of the services discussed as now the 1st service attracted most comments and time constraints made that less comments were provided for the last two services discussed. Alternative is to allocate fixed discussion time for all 3 sections of the footprint service.

2. Minutes of the 1st Time series Analysis service user panel consultation

Participants:

Live discussion : Damien Boulanger, Pawel Wolff, Valérie Thouret, Cathrine Lund Myhre, Claudio d'Onofrio, Carlos Ordonez, Susanne Rohs, Wenche Aas, Zois Zogopoulos, Lise Eder Murberg

Additional written comments : Audrey Gaudel

The meeting started at 14:00 until 15:40 on the 26th September. Valerie Thouret introduced the objectives of the meeting. Pawel Wolf ran the demonstration of the service with time for discussion at every step, led by Damien Boulanger. Damien and Lise Eder Murberg took the notes for the final report. VT concluded the meeting thanking the participants and recalling the importance of such user panel contributions to keep improving the service. Additional meetings with contributors from ACTRIS and IAGOS are planned.

Below are summarized the actions as discussed :

2.1 Information Tab and frame of the application

About the frame of the application:

- it's clear there are several consecutive steps but we should add a number for each step: 1 for search, 2 for select, etc.

About the information tab

- The list of variables and datasets available on this information page need to be updated. Right now there are some variables that are not available yet (e.g. Water Vapor from IAGOS).
- Links in general, like the DOI in the ICOS info, could/should be active links.

2.2 Search Datasets Tab

- It is unclear what the rectangles represent for IAGOS. Need to explain the dots (stations/profiles) and squares (regions). Therefore, it is proposed to change the marker at the centre of the rectangles (e.g. an aircraft)
- Need/Interest for Additional variables:
 - No further variables asked more than the Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) so far
 - New variables will depend on the datasets provided by the RIs

- IAGOS_H2O to be included (Relative humidity and H2O in ppm). Dataset of interest for contrails studies.
- Question about collocated sites:
 - they overlap right now so that one station is not visible in the map (ex. ACTRIS above ICOS).
 - Developer is aware of this, but there is a technical difficulty to correct this.
 - Solutions proposed: one is a larger marker than the other (you might see it better); or split the marker in two colors
- In the date range picker it should be easier to change the year
- A link should be added for each variable to get a small explanation of it. Proposition: link to the ECVs webpage: <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables/>
- Data outside of Europe should be made available as long as the datasets are provided by the RIs.
- Suggestion: “Search dataset” tab to be renamed “Search Variables and Locations”
- Suggestion: only stations which can provide the variables should be selectable.

2.3 Select Datasets

- For some users it took a while to understand that we have to click on the bars. Need to improve the documentation (e.g. info popup)
- The eye icon in the table for preview is not clear. Proposition: change for a more understandable icon.
- Discussion about problems to manage some ACTRIS datasets with several dimensions:
 - Problems to get out ACTRIS PNSD data and EC/OC data. Lacks absorption data.
 - Most of the ACTRIS might not work in the production version if the data has more than one temporal dimension. This is a bit better in the new development version, but still must be worked on.
 - A dedicated meeting to improve the visibility of ACTRIS data will be set up.
 - Some bugs to solve:
 - Selecting station IVI Ivittuut, ICOS, then selecting both datasets CO2 and press ‘select datasets’ resolves in Error: Internal application error. Please try another action and/or choose another dataset(s).
 - ICOS datasets are often ‘double’ visible (a request to check the collecting script is under way)
 - Suggestion: “Select Datasets” tab to be renamed “Select Time series” and then add a short sentence like “Click on the colored rectangles of the chart on the left to select the time series. For download purposes, choose up to 10 time

series. Once the list appears on the right, click on the eye to visualize the time series on a graph.”

2.4 Filter data

- Discussion about a “season” filter:
 - It’s not possible to only filter data for chosen season(s). Right now the time filter is only for continuous periods. This can be included but there is a difficulty since seasons are different considering the location;
 - A possibility would be to add some fields to define a season or the specific months the users want to keep and exclude the rest. However, due to time constraints, this is not the priority for implementation in the next 6 months.
- For the date range fields a date picker should be implemented.
- “Filter data” tab is busy and it takes time to understand how to use it. Maybe it would help to revise the font of the subtitles and have short sentences to explain what it is about. (e.g. when choosing the aerosols data, Difficult to understand the different variables).
- Suggestion: in addition to the % availability of the data, show the absolute number of data
- Suggestion: It would help to have a scrolling menu or a calendar menu for the filter in time

2.5 Data analysis

The three analysis tabs are not easy to find. Suggestion to change the font or the appearance of the tabs.

2.5.1 Exploratory analysis

- It would be nice to group variables on the same axis if they have the same unit. There could be problems if the unit is missing (in that case ignore the datasets) or have a different name (it’s a problem to be solved by the RIs)
- A manual input for min and max of the scales is planned (common scale for all variables)
- Rename “Gaussian mean” in “Arithmetic mean”. The name is “arithmetic mean” as opposed to other types of mean (e.g. geometric mean)
- Better describe the moving average with a pop-up window as information (and also the other methods)
- Combined (from clusters of stations) time series (from different datasets) is not possible for this exploratory analysis and is not planned in the given time frame. One solution, would be to create first an extra dataset merging data (under the responsibility of the RIs).

- Encountered issues to visualize the plots for monthly ozone and CO in the free troposphere. The warning message says that there is not enough data. It was because the aggregation period was not “year”. It would be helpful for the user to cut out the choices for aggregation periods when it doesn’t apply given the selected data.

2.5.2 Trend analysis

- Need to further describe the methods and explain the aggregate feature.
- Wondering if the methods will vary with species. For ozone, you can refer to TOAR work. It can be a nice outcome from TOAR. Do not hesitate to ask for help from this community.

2.5.3 Multivariate analysis

- Concern what is compared only over the overlapping time. The rest is cut out.
- Linear regression is not considered very useful. Comment from one user: “I assume you have used ordinary least squares, which only minimizes errors in the y variable to estimate the coefficients (a,b) of the regression $y = a + b \cdot x$. Because of this, the slope of that regression would not be consistent with that of $x = a' + b' \cdot y$. A better option could be reduced major axis regression, which handles errors in both the x and y variables. Both fields are observations, so there is no reason to prioritize one over the other.
- Providing R2 as you have done is fine (same value for $y \sim x$ and for $x \sim y$) assuming that the relationship between both fields is linear. If you wanted to account for linear and non-linear relationships you would have to provide two different correlation coefficients: a parametric one assuming linearity (Pearson, which is just the square root of the R2 value you calculated), and a non-parametric one (e.g., Spearman) that simply assumes a monotonic but not necessarily linear relationship between both fields.”

2.6 General feedback and perspectives

General remarks from the development team:

- User login and statistics of usage will soon be implemented for the service.
- Download of the data will be implemented very soon.

2.7 General feedback from the panel:

- Colors might not work with color blindness right now. This will be checked with a dedicated tool
(e.g. IPCC document: <https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2019/04/IPCC-visual-style-guide.pdf>).
- The possibility to change labels on some parts of the plots should be clearly explained somewhere. Since it is global, it should maybe be available on the information page

(suggestion: add lines above the graph like: X axis label, Y axis label, etc. like you find in some user-friendly software).

- The “download figure” button will be removed since it is possible to click on the camera icon of each plot (but need to be documented).
- Download is for the data that is calculated by the service, not the original data. Original data can be accessed directly at the RI (add the landing page links for this).
- “We have been criticizing this for the past 1 ½ hour, but we would like to comment that this is a very good tool.”
- Need to review the data access API (example of ICOS datasets in double): need to organize a meeting with RIs data centers to improve the API.
- “Really important tools. Thank you very much for putting this together.”
- Question: Should the figures from the tools be used in publications? Answer: yes it’s anticipated (watermark, edition of the labels, etc.)
- One general feedback would be to make users’ life easier by making the tool as simple and obvious as possible, with clear titles, subtitles, tab names, font easy to read, avoiding choices that do not apply, making clear the choices that do apply, etc....

2.8 Presentation of the VA services feedback form by Lise

- link: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access-feedback-form/>
- The link will be sent to all the members of the panel. It’s very important that everyone fills it.

